

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7978816

CORRECTION OF THE STATE OF THE BIOGEOMETRIC PROFILE OF THE POSTURE OF MEN IN THE SECOND PERIOD OF ADULTHOOD IN THE COURSE OF HEALTH FITNESS CLASSES: MODERN TREND

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Abstract. The object of the research is to substantiate, develop and test experimentally the effectiveness of the technology for correcting abnormalities of the biogeometric profile of the posture of men in the second period of adulthood in the course of health fitness classes, to increase its health-saving orientation. To solve the goals and objectives of the scientific work the use of a set of complementary research methods (theoretical, sociological, biomedical, pedagogical methods and mathematical statistics), their adequacy to the object, and subject were proved, the organization of the study and the contingent under research were described. It should be noted that while developing the technologies for correcting posture disorders in men in the second period of adulthood by means of health fitness, special attention should be paid to the features of the spatial organization of their bodies, and corrective and preventive complexes should be developed in accordance with the level of their biogeometric posture profiles. It was also noted that it is necessary to take into account not only levels of biogeometric posture profile, but also to take into account the indicators of functional assessment of movements.

Keywords: correction, disorder, condition, biogeometric posture profile, the second period of adulthood, functional assessment of movements, health fitness.

The object of the research is to substantiate, develop and test experimentally the effectiveness of the technology for correcting abnormalities of the biogeometric profile of the posture of men in the second period of adulthood in the course of health fitness classes, to increase its health-saving orientation.

For a wide range of researchers, the state of health of the modern population is of serious concern [1, 7, 14, 15]. Scientists note that the highest morbidity rate belongs to the class of circulatory system diseases, the second place is occupied by diseases of the organs, and the third rank is occupied by diseases of the musculoskeletal system [4, 5, 8, 10, 12]. The urgency of the problem of the awareness of the phenomenon of the spatial organization of the human body can be traced:

✓ in the late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries the growing trend of disorders of the spatial organization of the human body, in particular, a decrease in the state of biogeometric posture profile, is a thorny issue. It is the most relevant for the living conditions of humans in megapolises [3, 13, 17];

✓ the increasing value of human individuality in the modern world and increased perception of everything related to personal self-expression, and biogeometric posture profile is one of the characteristics of this individuality [2, 11];

✓ the formation of the spatial organization of the body in the conditions of modern civilization as one of the characteristics of physical health – a symbolic value [9, 10, 16];

✓ the increased importance for men of issues of image in the modern society as the ability to present themselves to the society in the proper state of the spatial organization of their bodies. The factors that affect the state of the spatial organization of the body of men were taken into consideration.

Taking into account the said above and the theoretical, practical and social significance of improving the health of adulthood people, the development of the technology for correcting the disorders of the biogeometric profile of the posture of men during the second period of adulthood in the course of health fitness classes to increase health-saving direction is quite timely and relevant.

To solve the goals and objectives of the scientific work the use of a set of complementary research methods (theoretical, sociological, biomedical, pedagogical methods and mathematical statistics), their adequacy to the object, and subject were proved, the organization of the study and the contingent under research were described.

The researches of the somatoscopic indicators of men of 36 – 45 years old on the stage of the ascertaining experiment indicate that among the persons under study the disturbance in the sagittal plane with the increase of physiological curves of the spine – flat back dominates: among men of 36 – 40 years old there were recorded 36.4 % and among men of 41 – 45 years old – 42.9 %. The distribution of 36-40-year-old men by levels of biogeometric posture profile showed that among men with normal posture, men with medium and high levels of biogeometric profile were equally distributed and their shares were 13.6 %. Moreover, among men with a round back there was a 9.1% larger proportion of low level than that of the medium level, as well as the patients with scoliotic posture in which the difference between the shares was 4.5 %, and among the men with a flat back, on the contrary, the proportion of the medium level of biogeometrical profile of posture dominated the share with a low level by 4.5 % [6].

The data of the ascertaining experiment allowed us to establish that the level of the biogeometric posture profile of 36-40-year-old men is (18.59; 6.12 points), and of 41 – 45-year-old men – (16.57; 4.82 points). It is worth noting that the level of the biogeometric profile of posture in the frontal plane of 36-40-year-old men is higher by 14.0 %, in the sagittal is higher by 8.23 %, and the overall level of the biogeometric profile of posture is higher by 10.9 % than that of 41-45-year-old men [6].

It has been found that the decrease in the biogeometric posture profile of men of both subgroups does not cause statistically significant ($p > 0.05$) changes in body length and weight. Taking this into account, while developing the technologies for correcting posture disorders in men in the second period of adulthood by means of health fitness, special attention should be paid to the features of the spatial organization of their bodies, and corrective and preventive complexes should be developed in accordance with the level of their biogeometric posture profiles [6].

The analysis of movement functional assessment (using the FMS (Functional Movement Screen) test system) and level of men's biogeometrical posture profile by pairwise comparisons of averages between the groups using the Duncan's ranking criterion for multivariate comparisons allowed to reveal the following: functional movement assessment in the group of men of 36-40 years old with a high level of biogeometrical posture profile is statistically significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than in the group of men with medium and low levels in both age subgroups. At the same time, the calculations have proved that in the group of men of 36-40 years old with the average

level of biometric posture profile functional movement assessment is statistically significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than in the group of men with a low level of both age subgroups; it should be noted that in the group of men of 36-40 years old with a low level of biometric posture profile the functional assessment of movement is statistically significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than in the group of men with a low level of both age subgroups; however, there are no statistically significant ($p > 0.05$) differences between the functional movement assessment of men with the same level of biometric posture profile depending on the age subgroup. The use of analysis of variance (ANOVA (Analysis of Variance)) allowed us to establish a statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) effect of the biometric profile of the posture of men of 36-45 years old on the endurance of the abdominal muscles and mobility of the hip joint and lumbar spine. The above data have indicated that in the process of developing the corrective and preventive measures for men in the second period of adulthood, it is necessary to take into account not only levels of their biometric posture profiles, but also to take into account the indicators of functional assessment of movements [6].

Based on the conducted ascertaining experiment, the author's technology was developed, which is based on the principles of consistency, unity of theory and practice, determinism, wellness orientation, and its conceptual basis is humanistic, axiological, personality-oriented, activity-based and technological approaches. The technology has got three stages: retracting, corrective, and supporting. It includes conceptual, organizational, diagnostic, informational, corrective, programming and methodical components and contains the assessment of the effectiveness of corrective and preventive measures based on certain criteria.

The analysis of the type of posture of men of 36-40 years of old after the experiment showed that among the men of 36-40 years old there were 31.8 % more men with normal posture than before the experiment. The 41-45-year-old men also showed positive changes in the type of posture: the proportion of men with normal posture increased by 17.9 %. The effectiveness of the proposed technology is evidenced by the results of assessing the state of the biometric profile of posture of men in the second adulthood. Thus, among the men of 36-40 years old with the normal posture the increase in the proportion of people with the normal posture who are characterized by the high level of biometric posture profile, was 22.8 % after the experiment, and by the medium level – 9.1 %. On the other hand, the proportion of people with the round back, who had the medium and low biometric posture profile before the experiment, decreased by 4.5% and 18.2%, respectively. A similar pattern was observed within the men of 41-45 years old, the proportion of people with normal posture with a high level of biometric posture profile increased by 17.9 %. Comparing the obtained results with the results of the previous research, it was found that after the experiment there was a statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in both indicators of the biometric posture profile in the sagittal and frontal planes of men of 36-40 years old as well as in the overall assessment of their biometric posture profile [6].

After the implementation of the author's technology in the process of health fitness classes for the men in the second period of adulthood, there was an improvement in the functional assessment of their movement. The fact is that in the group of 36-40 years old men for all (seven) of the test exercises there has been observed statically significant ($p < 0.05$) improvement in functional assessment of movement; much the same happened in the group of 41-45 years old men, the only exception was for the test exercise with the help of which the agility of shoulder girdle was estimated, where statistically significant ($p > 0.05$) changes didn't occur, but at the same time, positive dynamics of the indicator under the study was shown. It was determined that the

use of the author's technology contributed to the increase of physical fitness of the men of the second adulthood: it showed a statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in the endurance of the abdominal muscles of the men of both subgroups, and in the group of the men of 36–40 years old this increase was 7.85 %, and in the group of the men of 41–45 years old – 7.83 %. Moreover, after the experiment, we were able to record statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) positive changes in the mobility of the hip joint and lumbar spine in the group of men who took part in the experiment [6].

The effectiveness of the author's technology has been experimentally confirmed which gives us all the grounds to recommend it for the practical implementation in the process of health fitness classes for the men of adulthood [6].

The factual material presented in the paper and the generalizations and conclusions made on its basis are important for improving the effectiveness of the process of health fitness classes.

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